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Historical Sciences

SPORTS AND RECREATION ACTIVITIES AS AN IMPORTANT FACTOR IN THE EDUCATION OF YOUNG PEOPLE IN RUSSIA

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Abstract

The article deals with physical education of young people in Russia in the context of negative trends in modern society. The multidimensional and multi-level study of the phenomenon of physical culture made it possible to generalize particular approaches to understanding the essence of physical culture on the basis of cultural and pedagogical methodology, to clarify the interaction of physical culture with other types of culture and determine its place in the system of cultural values of a person and society, to reveal the systemic nature and interrelation of its value-normative, institutional and activity aspects.

Keywords: culture, education, sport, society, country.

I. INTRODUCTION

The problems of improving the level of physical education have recently become particularly relevant. This is primarily due to its objective role in improving the quality of human life. The level of development of physical culture, health and active longevity are the most important prerequisites for the realization of human potential and are currently considered one of the leading criteria for social progress.

The relevance of the research topic is also related to the strengthening of negative trends in the structure of the lifestyle of modern youth, which have negative consequences for the health of both the individual and society as a whole. The level of psychophysical culture is significantly reduced, which is associated with a sharp increase in information and emotional stress, poor technological equipment of the population to overcome stressful situations.

The decrease in the level of health of the population is confirmed by an increase in deviant behavior (alcohol, drugs), an increase in the number of psychopathologies and a decrease in the overall health indicators of people.

The other extreme of this problem is an excessive fascination with instrumental sports indicators, the absolutization of physical characteristics of a person.

As a result, a one-sided personality is formed, unable to reveal its potential, revealed by nature. Thus, the relevance of the article lies in the contradiction of the objective potential of physical education in improving physical and motor qualities, enriching the spiritual world of a person, creating conditions for self-realization of an individual in the context of an educational environment.

II. METHODOLOGY

The research methodology was based on a set of mutually complementary methods of sociological, socio-psychological and, above all, pedagogical analysis. The leading research methods were various modifications of observations, surveys, interviews, and expert assessment.

A special place was taken by a socio-pedagogical experiment on the basis of the Department of Physical Education of Voronezh State Technical University. The subject of scientific analysis was physical education as part of the student grid hours, as well as the work of sports sections and schools.

III. DISCUSSION

The study of the various facets of the phenomenon of physical culture has its own history, the established methodology, categorical apparatus. A large volume of publications is devoted to the optimization of the conditions for the formation of physical culture and the improvement of the process of physical education (V.U. Ageevets, A.G. Barabanov, P.V. Bundzen, P.A. Vinogradov, M.Ya. Vilensky, Yu.A. Gagin, S.P. Evseev, I.M. Kozlov, V.F. Kostyuchenko, V.I. Lyakh, L.P. Matveev).

Of greatest interest in the context of this article is the study of Yu.M. Nikolayeva, in which physical culture is analyzed in the ratio of biological and social, bodily and spiritual in a person, and is considered from the perspective of the macrostructure and data from interdisciplinary research. Physical exercises as a kind of activity slice of culture from the point of view of their influence on a person are considered by as a methodological basis for understanding the multifaceted and integrative essence of physical culture as a whole, the formation of its theory, the most complete realization of its potential in the pedagogical process.

For all the breadth of the development of problems of physical culture in studies of recent years, there have been significant contradictions between the high objective requirements of society for health, physical development, physical fitness of people and the low level of development of physical culture.

IV. RESULTS

A systematic study of various aspects and facets of physical culture has shown that an adequate understanding of the nature and functions of physical culture, its true role and place both in individual life and in the history of human civilizations is an essential factor in optimizing the functioning of physical culture.

This understanding is provided on the basis of a socio-pedagogical methodology that can combine existing approaches to the study of various aspects of physical culture and reinterpret information obtained in various areas of social and humanitarian knowledge.

Changes in physical activity needs with increasing age of children and adolescents.

The implementation of the socio-cultural approach of the methodology makes it possible to increase the effectiveness of special training for managers and organizers of physical education by strengthening the historical and cultural aspects of physical culture, adapting various cultural practices focused on the development and improvement of the physical and mental nature of a person. Cultural analysis provides a methodological basis for overcoming the contradiction in the system of physical education and upbringing between the historical, cultural and technological potential of physical culture and the level of its development in the educational process by expanding the educational issues, developing programs that ensure the development of not only technological, but also spiritual, valuable, intellectual wealth of physical culture, to optimize the social conditions of physical culture functioning, which should be considered as a direct object of targeted state policy.

At the same time, the effectiveness of the state policy in the field of physical culture will largely be determined by its focus on the approval of a healthy lifestyle in the public consciousness as a socio-cultural and personal value.

V. CONCLUSION

The definition of the essence of physical culture, its levels allowed us to clarify those aspects of it that can and should be considered as the subject of historical and cultural analysis. The cultural aspect of the analysis, fixing the inseparable unity of the value-normative and technological aspects of physical culture, allows to significantly increase the role and importance of the personal factor, which, in turn, is a necessary condition for building a system of physical education, taking into account the understanding of the integral essence of a person, his natural and spiritual, somatopsychic and socio-cultural unity.

The theoretical results of the cultural analysis of physical culture expand the boundaries of understanding the essence and functions of this phenomenon, and determine the directions for further research of physical culture as a socio-cultural phenomenon.

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ФИЗКУЛЬТУРНО-ОЗДОРОВИТЕЛЬНАЯ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТЬ КАК ВАЖНЫЙ ФАКТОР ВОСПИТАНИЯ МОЛОДЁЖИ В РОССИИ

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Аннотация

Статья посвящена проблеме физического воспитания молодежи в России в контексте негативных тенденций современного общества.

Многомерное и многоуровневое изучение феномена физической культуры позволило обобщить частные подходы к пониманию сущности физической культуры на основе культурно-педагогической методологии, уточнить взаимодействие физической культуры с другими видами культуры и определить ее место в системе культурных ценностей личности и общества, выявить системный характер и взаимосвязь ее ценностно-нормативного, институционального и деятельностного аспектов.

Ключевые слова: культура, образование, спорт, общество, страна.

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